

THE HISTORY OF KASHGAR RUBOBI'S PERFORMANCE AND ITS PLACE IN THE ORCHESTRA

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Annotation: This article covers the history of Kashgar rubobi's performance and its place in the orchestra.

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A deeper and more comprehensive study of our national music culture from Khar kung, its widespread promotion in the people, is one of the pressing issues of today. A special place in Uzbek music is occupied by the Kashgar rubob, along with many instruments. This instrument has become one of the favorite instruments of our people with its resonances and proximity to the human heart, and its unimaginable ease in terms of learning and performance. Skillful musicians such as muhammadjan Mirzaev, Ergash Shukrullaev, Abbas Bakhromov, Ari Bobokhanov, Suleiman Taxalov, Kabil Usmanov, Toxir Rajabov and Adham Khudoyqulov added a great deal in making Kashgar rubobi more beloved and popular within our people. Kashgar rhubarb is widespread not only in our republic, but also in Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, the Kyrgyz republics and many oases. After all, in this instrument, along with folk melodies, it is possible to masterfully perform all the songs of our brothers, compositions by composers, complex works in every way.

The kashkar rubab is distributed from the Kashkar. Hence the name Kashkar rubab. The kashkar rubab is 80-100 cm long. The ladle bowl of kashkar rubab is made from the wood of hardwoods such as Mulberry. The top of the bowl is covered with skin. The stalk of the kashkar rubab is long and the end is recurved. In front of his bowl

are two gajagi that look like a horn. As well as giving shape, they also act as a support for the left hand when playing high notes. The kashkar rubab stalk contains 19 to 23 veils. In old rubobs, curtains are made of gut, while in modern rubobs, curtains are made of metal. The kashkar rubab has five cables. The 5 tori of the kashkar rubab are usually tuned in the quart-Quinta range. The bottom two wire rings in pairs. When played open it is tuned to produce a "lya" sound. Strings 3 and 4 are also played in pairs. The strings are tuned to make a "mi" sound when played open. String 5 is usually a nylon string and is tuned to make the sound of "si" when played open. The range of the kashkar rubab is about 3 octaves.

The sound of the rubab is resonant. The unimaginable lightness of mastering the performance, the maturation of skillful rubab-musicians (Muhammadjan Mirzayev and others) caused the sound to become popular among amateur and professional musicians in Uzbekistan and Tajikistan from the 1940s. The reworked modern type of kashkar rubab, the rubob prima, is tuned in its capabilities close to the Russian domra, in the range of 4 Metal tori Quinta. It is used in orchestra and as a solo sound. Muhammadjan Mirzayev of Uzbek composers, A. Bobokhanov, N. Qulabdullayev, composers Ibrahim Hamroyev, Mustafa Bafoyev and others have created works for qashqar rubobi in various genres.

Kashkar rubab is also a.I.Modernized under Petrosyans. The bolted curtains on a brown rubbery handle, with sturdy curtains mounted on the handle, have the diatonic reverberator replaced by a 12-stage equally tempered chromatic reverberator. Also created on the basis of the Kashkar rubab were the prima rubab, metsosoprano rubab, little rubab and alt rubab. These instruments are now widely used as soloists and horn players as part of ensembles and orchestras. Also, in all educational institutions of the Republic, lessons are taught on Kashkar rubob classes.

For the emergence of professional education in Uzbek folk instruments, the issue of organizing special classes and training of qualified pedagogical personnel arose. Thus the kushnay, chang, prima rubab, kashkar rubab, dutor, dutor bas, doira, gijjak,

may, gijjak alt, kobuz bas, kobuz double bass in 1948, bayan in 1950, surnay in 1951, Afghan rubab and tanbur classes were opened in 1963 years.

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